

Engaging Researchers with Data Management: The Cookbook

Exploring Past, Present, and Future Outcomes of the RDA Libraries for Research Data (L4RD) IG

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RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

UNITED STATES

rd-alliance.org

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Today's talk... The next 10 minutes!

- The Cookbook
- Project organisation
- Project timeline
- The book sprint
- How to use the Cookbook
- The case studies (three examples)

Open Book Publishers

<https://www.openbookpublishers.com/product/1080>

pdf, html, paper or hardback

- 24 innovative case studies
- Institutions around the world
- Activities for effectively engaging researchers with data management

- For anyone interested in RDM
- Raise awareness of best practices
- Inform and inspire implementation

Engaging Researchers with Data Management The Cookbook

CONNIE CLARE, MARIA CRUZ, ELI PAPADOPOULOU, JAMES SAVAGE,
MARTA TEPEREK, YAN WANG, IZA WITKOWSKA, AND JOANNE YEOMANS

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Project organisation (L4RD)

Engaging researchers with Research Data: What works?

Project lead: Marta Teperek (TU Delft/4TU.ResearchData)

Steering board (10): Lauren Cadwallader, Julien Colomb, Maria Cruz, Mary Donaldson, Lambert Heller, Rosie Higman, Elli Papadopoulou, Vanessa Proudman, James Savage, Marta Teperek

Task leaders (6): Julien Colomb, Maria Cruz, Raman Ganguly, Reme Melero, Marta Teperek, Iza Witkowska

Authors & editors (8): Connie Clare, Maria Cruz, Elli Papadopoulou, James Savage, Marta Teperek, Yan Wang, Iza Witkowska, Joanne Yeomans

Libraries for Research Data IG: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/libraries-research-data.html>

Project timeline

Project outline

IDW 2018
RDA 12th Plenary meeting,
Botswana

Survey template & data collection

60 funders, 80 institutions
28 mailing lists

216 responses, 50 unique
institutions, 88 activities

Update: Analysis & case study selection

RDA 13th Plenary meeting,
Philadelphia

GitHub, quantitative data analysis,
categorisation, steering board
selection and interview
contributors

Publication & promotion

Peer-review, editing,
publication and
presentation at RDA 14th
Plenary meeting, Helsinki

Three-day book sprint

8 authors/editors draft case studies
in Den Haag (Netherlands)

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The book sprint

Book Sprint Success: A Team Writing Exercise For The Win.

A collaborative writing exercise in <1 week

- Three-day book sprint
- Den Haag (Netherlands)
- Authors draft assigned case studies

- Set out the goals and objectives
- Come prepared with content
- Schedule blocks, briefs and breaks!
- Have fun!

How to use the Cookbook

- Navigate case studies of interest/relevant
- The Cookbook = recipes with ingredients
- Number of researchers
- Number of PhDs
- Number of RDM support staff
- Target audience (first stage, recognised, established, leading)
- Main driver (top down, bottom up, researcher-led, disciplinary, centrally coordinated)
- Cost (materials, infrastructure, time)
 - Inexpensive to expensive
- Ease of implementation (very easy to difficult)

The Cookbook Chapters

1. Research Data Management Policy: The Holy Grail of Research Data Management Support

2. Finding triggers for engagement

3. Engagement through training

4. Dedicated events to Gauge Interest and Build Networks

8. Engage with Senior Researchers through Archiving

7. Interviews and Case Studies

5. Networks of Data Champions

6. Dedicated consultants to offer one-to-one support with data

Case study: Finding triggers for engagement

Seeking opportunities for engagement and adapt existing workflows

Taking Advantage of Existing Administrative Systems at the MRC Social and Public Health sciences Unit, University of Glasgow (Mary-Kate Hannah, Data Scientist)

- Researcher applies for grant
- Complete an online form
- Sent to 'Portfolio Group' for approval
- Check topic within unit's remit
- Resources identified (personnel, data storage, DMPonline)
- Automatic email to Mary-Kate
- RDM presentation
- Follow-up: trial master file (grant application, legal, RDM folders)

Case study: Engagement through training

Using low-cost training methods to support researchers

Bring your own data workshop at the University of Cambridge (Annemarie Hildegard Eckes-Shephard, researcher)

- Researcher-led, bottom-up initiative
- RDM & Open Science starts with good project organisation
- Monthly 2 hr informal workshop
- Official calendar event
 - File-naming conventions
 - Writing a README
 - File and folder structure
- Peer-to-peer
- Networking and collaboration

Case study: Interviews and case studies

Increasing the visibility of RDM teams and services

Showcasing peers and their good practice at Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam & Utrecht University (Annemiek van der Kuil & Anneke de Maat, data supporters)

- Interview researchers & publish stories
- Illustrate the value of RDM best practices
- Highlight lead by example, impact and visibility, raise the profile of ECR to senior researchers
- Peer-driven examples influence others
- 'Social norms govern the behaviour of society members'
- More researchers know where to seek help!

Thank you for your attention!

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